

SOME ALIPHATIC MONOCARBOXYLATE COMPLEXES OF BIVALENT METALS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART V. COBALT ACETATO COMPLEXES

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The p_H values of aqueous solution mixtures of cobalt acetate and nitric acid at different concentrations, after attainment of equilibrium, have been determined. The data obtained have been utilised to calculate the thermodynamic dissociation constants, K_1 and K_2 , for the two successive equilibria $\text{CoAc}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CoAc}^+ + \text{Ac}^-$ and $\text{CoAc}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Co}^{2+} + \text{Ac}^-$, applying a modification of Bjerrum's method described in Part III of the series. The values found at 29.31° are $K_1 = 260 \times 10^{-3}$ and $K_2 = 30.2 \times 10^{-3}$.

Cobalt acetate dissociates in aqueous solution in two stages :

The first and second thermodynamic dissociation constants of cobalt acetate are therefore given by

$$K_1 = \frac{c_{\text{CoAc}^+} \cdot c_{\text{Ac}^-}}{c_{\text{CoAc}_2}} \cdot \frac{f_{\text{CoAc}^+} \cdot f_{\text{Ac}^-}}{f_{\text{CoAc}_2}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(1)}$$

and
$$K_2 = \frac{c_{\text{Co}^{2+}} \cdot c_{\text{Ac}^-}}{c_{\text{CoAc}^+}} \cdot \frac{f_{\text{Co}^{2+}} \cdot f_{\text{Ac}^-}}{f_{\text{CoAc}^+}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(2)}$$

In Part IV of this work the second dissociation constant, ' K_2 ', of cobalt acetate has already been determined (this issue, p. 339). In the present paper, by employing a modification of Bjerrum's method ("Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Sons, 1941) of determining the consecutive dissociation constants, both the first and second dissociation constants ' K_1 ' and ' K_2 ' have been found out. Essentially, in the present paper, the same procedure as adopted in Part III of this series (this issue, p. 323) has been followed, where theoretical details on the method have been discussed.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Cobalt acetate pure (Johnson and Sons, Scales brand) was purified by crystallising first from acetic acid and then from absolute alcohol, when a pink coloured anhydrous salt was obtained (Ephraim and Rosenberg, *Ber.*, 1918, 51, 134). [Found: Co (as sulphate), 32.80. Calc. for $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{Co}$, 33.32%].

Stock solutions of cobalt acetate and nitric acid (A.R.) were prepared and cobalt and nitric acid in them were estimated in the usual way. Such measured

volumes of stock solutions were mixed, that on dilution to 10 c.c., they produced the desired initial concentrations C' and C_a for cobalt acetate and nitric acid respectively. After keeping the solution mixtures in a closed room for 2 hours, the p_H values were determined by following the same procedure and precautions as in Part IV (this issue, p. 339) of this series.

TABLE I

The symbols used in the table headings and their evaluations are same as in Part III (*loc. cit.*).

* $C_a = 0.015$.

Solu. No.	C'	t°	p_H	$\frac{a_A \times 10^3}{(K_a = 1.80 \times 10^{-5})}$	$a_A \times \frac{C-x}{2C-x} \times 10^3$	$a_A^{-2} \times \frac{x}{2C-x} \times 10^3$
1	0.012	29.7	4.205	4.30	- 6.45	0.0740
2	0.0135	"	4.305	5.45	- 5.87	0.0937
3	0.015	"	4.405	6.86	- 5.83	0.1272
4	0.018	29.5	4.523	9.00	- 4.50	0.1619
5	0.020	30.6	4.587	10.43	- 3.86	0.1892
6	0.021	29.5	4.615	11.13	- 3.57	0.2033
7	0.024	"	4.681	12.95	- 2.59	0.2348
8	0.030	30.6	4.838	18.60	- 2.54	0.4402
9	0.040	"	4.953	24.24	+ 0.475	0.5644
10	0.050	"	5.040	29.61	+ 2.89	0.7057
11	0.065	29.8	5.12	35.58	+ 6.45	0.8069
12	0.078	"	5.10	40.85	+ 9.02	0.9317
13	0.0845	"	5.20	42.80	+ 10.28	0.9519
14	0.091	"	5.22	44.78	+ 11.44	0.9813
15	0.0975	"	5.24	46.96	+ 12.53	1.028
16	0.104	"	5.26	49.09	+ 13.61	1.074
17	0.117	"	5.29	52.64	+ 15.66	1.126
18	0.120	29.7	5.30	53.91	+ 16.10	1.170
19	0.140	"	5.35	60.40	+ 19.06	1.345
20	0.160	"	5.37	63.24	+ 21.40	1.293
21	0.170	"	5.38	64.76	+ 22.45	1.286
22	0.180	"	5.39	66.34	+ 23.50	1.284

* C and C_a denote respectively molar concentration of CoAc_2 and HNO_3 .

Table I shows the experimental p_H values and the corresponding values of the functions

$$a_A \cdot \frac{C-x}{2C-x} \times 10^3 \quad \text{and} \quad a_A^{-2} \cdot \frac{x}{2C-x} \times 10^3$$

(where A^- stands for acetate ion and ' x ', total concentration of "free acetic acid species" given by $c_A^- + C_a$). Fig. 1 represents equation (5b) (vide Part III, *loc. cit.*)

FIG. 1

(Ordinate magnified 20 times that of abscissa).

c.l.) graphically. (For solutions of low ionic strengths ' c_A ' may be put equal to ' a_A ' in equation 5b). The slope and intercept on the ordinate, of the straight line curve obtained, give the values of k_1 and k_2 as respectively 50.0×10^{-3} and 8.00×10^{-3} . These may be regarded as the average values of k_1 and k_2 over the range of ionic strengths employed.

TABLE II

The symbols used in the table headings and their evaluations are same as in Part III (*loc. cit.*).

Solu. No (same as in Table I.)	Method of calculation.	$c_{MA} \times 10^3$.	$c_{M^+} \times 10^3$.	μ .	$c_A \times 10^3$ (using $K_3 =$ 1.75×10^{-3}).	$X \times 10^3$.	$Y \times 10^3$.
1	(a)	4.09	7.60	0.02689	5.10	-4.902	0.0422
	(b)	4.01	7.65	0.02695	5.10	-4.897	0.0421
2	(a)	5.18	7.61	0.02803	6.42	-4.075	0.0480
	(b)	5.37	7.54	0.02799	6.45	-4.210	0.0494
3	(a)	6.56	7.65	0.02951	8.16	-4.343	0.0672
	(b)	6.38	7.74	0.02960	8.16	-4.339	0.0671
4	(a)	8.64	7.68	0.03168	10.78	-3.556	0.0836
	(b)	8.82	7.59	0.03159	10.78	-3.559	0.0837
5	(a)	10.02	7.69	0.03310	12.56	-3.226	0.0966
	(b)	10.28	7.58	0.03301	12.55	-3.241	0.0968
6	(a)	10.72	7.70	0.03382	13.42	-3.091	0.1032
	(b)	10.98	7.58	0.03371	13.42	-3.059	0.1033
7	(a)	12.50	7.72	0.03566	15.73	-2.523	0.1163
	(b)	13.30	7.28	0.03513	15.69	-2.514	0.1165
8	(a)	18.05	7.77	0.04136	22.95	-3.174	0.216
	(b)	15.13	9.24	0.04284	23.05	-3.196	0.214
9	(a)	23.63	7.80	0.04703	30.40	-1.709	0.2629
	(b)	20.69	9.28	0.04852	30.51	-1.732	0.2603

TABLE II (contd.)

Soln.	Method	$c_{M^+} \times 10^3$	$c_{M^-} \times 10^3$	μ	$c_A^- \times 10^3$	$X \times 10^3$	$Y \times 10^3$
10	(a)	28.95	7.82	0.05242	37.66	-0.719	0.314
	(b)	25.35	9.63	0.05424	37.83	-0.758	0.310
11	(a)	34.89	7.84	0.05841	45.97	+0.862	0.3398
	(b)	34.77	8.91	0.05949	45.05	+0.838	0.336
12	(a)	40.14	7.85	0.06369	53.40	+1.787	0.360
	(b)	38.02	8.92	0.06477	53.54	+1.752	0.3738
13	(a)	42.07	7.86	0.06565	56.21	+2.293	0.3783
	(b)	41.00	8.40	0.06620	56.27	+2.274	0.3777
14	(a)	44.04	7.87	0.06765	59.12	+2.726	0.3841
	(b)	43.78	8.00	0.06779	59.10	+2.724	0.3829
15	(a)	46.21	7.87	0.06982	62.20	+3.098	0.3941
	(b)	46.22	7.87	0.06983	62.27	+3.091	0.3951
16	(a)	48.34	7.87	0.07195	65.39	+3.434	0.407
	(b)	48.55	7.77	0.07186	65.37	+3.436	0.407
17	(a)	51.87	7.88	0.07551	70.75	+4.102	0.4176
	(b)	53.56	7.04	0.07468	70.52	+4.144	0.4180
18	(a)	53.13	7.89	0.07680	72.51	+4.202	0.4282
	(b)	54.02	7.86	0.07627	72.45	+4.226	0.4301
19	(a)	59.61	7.89	0.08328	82.41	+4.956	0.4742
	(b)	59.89	7.76	0.08316	82.39	+4.960	0.4744
20	(a)	62.44	7.90	0.08614	86.80	+5.830	0.444
	(b)	68.49	4.92	0.08320	86.25	+5.976	0.4512
21	(a)	63.95	7.90	0.08765	88.98	+6.195	0.4331
	(b)	72.48	3.64	0.08340	88.36	+6.407	0.4456
22	(a)	65.54	7.96	0.08924	91.58	+6.518	0.4268
	(b)	76.26	2.54	0.08388	90.62	+6.796	0.4429

The values of ' μ ', ' X ' and ' Y ', calculated by the two independent methods (a) and (b), described in Part III of this series (*loc. cit.*), have been shown in Table II. The values of ' Y ' and ' X ' from Table II, calculated by methods (a) and (b), are plotted in Figs. 2A and 2B respectively. It will be found on examination that both the two straight lines in Figs. 2A and 2B are identical in respect of slope and intercept on the ordinate, and hence, the values of ' K_1 ' and ' K_2 ' obtained from both are identical and are respectively 47.3×10^{-3} and 5.50×10^{-3} . These are not, however, the final values (*vide* Discussion).

DISCUSSION

As explained in Part III (*loc. cit.*), the values of ' K_1 ' and ' K_2 ' obtained in the present paper are graphically taken mean values containing a mean error corresponding to the mean ionic strength for the solutions studied. This point can be substantiated, in the present case too, by plotting $pK_2 = (-\log K_2) = 2.2596$ found from the value of $K_2 = 5.50 \times 10^{-3}$ obtained above, against $\sqrt{\mu}_{\text{mean}} = 0.2388$, calculated from the values of ' μ ' in Table II, on the $pK/\sqrt{\mu}$ plot shown in Fig. 2, Part IV (*loc. cit.*). The point representing $pK/\sqrt{\mu}_{\text{mean}}$ in the present case (shown by solar sign mark in Fig. 2, Part IV) will be seen to fall on the straight line curve representing $pK_2/\sqrt{\mu}$ obtained from the data in Part IV.

FIG. 2A

FIG. 2B

(Ordinate magnified 10 times that of abscissa).

As has already been explained in Part III, the ratio K_1/K_2 , obtained in this communication, may be taken to be correct, while the value of ' K_2 ' determined in Part IV (*loc. cit.*) is essentially correct; therefore a correct value of ' K_1 ' can now be calculated out. The correct values are therefore $K_1 = 260.0 \times 10^{-5}$ and $K_2 = 30.2 \times 10^{-5}$ at 29.31° .

The only previous work on this subject appears to be that of Bardhan and Aditya (this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 109) who from a measurement of the E.M.F. of the cell conclude that the first stage dissociation of cobalt acetate in aqueous solution represented by equation (A) is virtually complete, and the thermodynamic constant for the equilibrium (B) representing the second stage dissociation is given by $K_2 = 43.5 \times 10^{-5}$ at 35° . In our opinion, the conclusion of the above authors about the first stage of dissociation being complete, is rather an assumption than a definite conclusion. The authors calculated the value of the degree of dissociation ' β ' for the second stage, assuming that the first stage dissociation was complete. Since the value of ' β ', thus calculated from the E.M.F. data, ranged from 0.95 to 0.60 for different dilutions of cobalt nitrate and sodium acetate solutions, they argued, "the values of ' β ' show that complete dissociation of the first stage is justified." Had the first stage of dissociation been considered at the very outset, the values of ' β ' would have been otherwise in our opinion.

On the other hand, we can establish definitely from the data obtained in the present work that the first step dissociation for cobalt acetate is substantially incomplete by the following considerations. If the first step dissociation is complete, the value of 'x' (free acetate species: $c_{Ac^-} + c_{HAc}$) for any solution mixtures of cobalt acetate (conc. C) and nitric acid (conc. C_n) should be always much greater than 'C'. The maximum ionic strength possible for such solution mixtures is equal to "3C", which is attained when even the second stage dissociation is complete*. The value of activity coefficient ' f_1 ' of acetate ion, calculated from this maximum possible value of ' μ ', would be the minimum possible value of ' f_1 ' for the solution mixture. If we calculate c_{Ac^-} from equation (8b) (Part III, *loc. cit.*), using this minimum value of ' f_1 ', that value would be maximum possible for c_{Ac^-} , and the value of 'x', calculated from this c_{Ac^-} , would also be maximum possible. It will be seen from Table III that for some of the solution mixtures (viz. No. 15 to 22), the value of x/c , thus calculated, hardly exceeds one. If the complete first step dissociation preceded any pronounced second step dissociation, the value of 'x' could not have been so low, particularly in view of the fact that there is additional decomposition of $CoAc^+$ species in presence of the nitric acid.

TABLE III

[The values of x considering the first step dissociation to be complete].

Soln. No. (as per Table I)	$\mu = 3C.$	$f_1.$	$c_{Ac^-} = \frac{K_a C_n}{a_{H^+} f_1}$	$x = c_{Ac^-} + C_n.$	$x/c.$
15	0.2925	0.5299	0.0861	0.1011	1.03
16	0.312	0.5189	0.0920	0.1070	1.02
17	0.351	0.4956	0.1026	0.1176	1.005
18	0.360	0.4943	0.1060	0.1210	1.008
19	0.420	0.4672	0.1256	0.1406	1.004
20	0.480	0.4433	0.1386	0.1536	0.96
21	0.510	0.4323	0.1456	0.1606	0.94
22	0.540	0.4220	0.1528	0.1678	0.93

It may therefore be concluded that the results obtained in the present work are more reliable than those of Bardhan and Aditya (*loc. cit.*) who start with an *ad hoc* assumption which is observed to be against experimental facts.

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$\mu = \frac{1}{2} [4 c_{Co^{++}} + (2c_{Ac^-} - c_{HAc}) + c_{H^+} + c_{NO_3^-}] = \frac{1}{2} [4C + 2C - C_n + C_n] = 3C$ assuming complete dissociation for cobalt acetate into cobalt and acetate ions and knowing the facts that $c_{NO_3} = C_n = c_{HAc}$ and c_{H^+} is negligible.